

The Role of Social Media in Shaping Students Narcissic Behavior

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Role, Social Media, TikTok, Narcissistic Behavior.

Received : 20, September

Revised : 25, October

Accepted: 28, November

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ABSTRACT

The background to this research is the researcher's interest in the social phenomenon that is currently occurring, namely the use of social media TikTok among class XI students at Cimenteng Pagelaran High School. Therefore, researchers want to know whether the social media TikTok has a role in building self-confidence, thereby giving rise to students' narcissistic behavior. The research aims to determine the role of TikTok social media on students' narcissistic behavior. The subjects of this research consisted of 3 students who were active users of the social media TikTok in class XI Science at Cimenteng Pagelaran High School. The theoretical basis used was New Media from Pierre Levy. This research uses a qualitative method with a phenomenological approach. The data collection activities used were interviews and documentation. The research results show that social media has a role in shaping students' narcissistic behavior.

INTRODUCTION

Technological developments are developing very quickly, resulting in changes in human life patterns. Sources of getting information have also changed, not just sticking to newspapers, magazines, radio and so on. One of them is the emergence of the internet network and the rapid development of technology in devices or gadgets. One of the changes with the rapid development of technology is in the behavioral patterns of teenagers, now it is not only adults who use smartphones. Teenagers are also required to be able to access the internet because learning media have started to use gadgets and digital technology.

As technology develops, many new applications emerge that can attract the attention of users *smartphone*. One of them is the emergence of the TikTok application which has succeeded in attracting the attention of users *smartphone* in all circles, including teenagers. The Tik Tok application is an application that is used to record, edit and upload to several social media, so that it can be seen by friends all over the world. What makes it different is that the Tik Tok application has various features that you can enjoy when making videos. There is *special effect* When making a video, of course it will give uniqueness to your homemade video so that it becomes an interesting video. That way, TikTok users can create very interesting short videos to show off to other people. The emergence of this application allows its users to express their self-confidence by publishing themselves through uploaded video content. Unconsciously, sometimes uploading videos to TikTok social media will receive praise which directly affects students' psychological conditions. Santrock (2011:437) explains that narcissism is an approach towards other people that is self-centered (*self-centered*) and think of yourself (*self-concerned*). Usually perpetrators of narcissism are not aware of their own actual situation and how other people perceive them. This ignorance creates adjustment problems for them. Narcissists are very self-centered, always emphasizing that they are perfect (*self-congratulatory*), and considering their desires and hopes is important.

From the end of July 2020 to October 2020, TikTok managed to add around 14.3 million monthly active users worldwide every month. Still in the same report, 47 percent of users said that they were tempted to buy something after watching content on TikTok. Meanwhile, 67 percent of users said that TikTok inspired them to buy things they had never previously planned. According to the report, 42 percent of TikTok users come from young people (Generation Z) with an age range of 18-24 years. The results of this research also say that the average user spends 89 minutes a day accessing the TikTok application.

On Tuesday 3 July 2018 MENKOMINFO (Ministry of Communication and Information) blocked the TikTok application after receiving several negative reports appearing on the TikTok application from the public. The blocking of this phenomenal application is based on the monitoring results of the AIS or MESS team in Kominfo internet scavenging. Not only that, Kominfo admitted that reports that TikTok should be blocked also came from the Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection, the Child Protection

Commission, as well as reports from levels of society. Rudiantara said, "*platform* TikTok is actually very good for children to express creativity. However, there are some users who abuse the application, said Minister of Communication and Information Rudiantara." "The blocking is temporary until there is improvement and cleaning up of illegal content from TikTok," said the Director General of Informatics Applications, Kominfo, Samuel Abrijani. Content violations found on the platform include pornographic content, immoral content, religious harassment content and so on. Until finally, after a temporary blocking was carried out on July 10 2018, the TikTok application was finally reopened by developing its security system and also artificial intelligence to help filter negative content.

The concern that is of concern is the phenomenon of using TikTok social media among students, especially at Cimenteng Pagelaran High School, namely the existence of content that does not reflect a student because of trends on TikTok social media, one of which is narcissistic behavior. The aim of this research is to find out how much time students use TikTok social media in class on Cimenteng Pagelaran High School students.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

This research uses theory New Media presented by Pierre Levy, in this theory displays the development of the media There are two views in new media theory, the first is the social interaction view, which differentiates media based on their closeness to face-to-face interaction. Pierre Levy argues World Wide Web (WWW) is an information environment that is flexible and dynamic, open, and allows people to develop new knowledge and engage in a democratic world of mutual and power-giving based on a more interactive society.

Meanwhile, the second approach is the social integration view, media is ritualized because media becomes a habit, something formal, and has great value from the use of media itself, or how humans use media as a way of creating society. Media is not just an instrument of information or a way to achieve self-interest, but unites us in some form of society and gives us a sense of belonging. New media is media online which is technology-based, flexible and interactive, functions both publicly and private by using the internet (Mondy, 2008: 13).

More briefly, Livingstone (1996 : 65) wrote "What is new about the internet is perhaps the combination and interactivity with features that are innovative for mass communication, the unlimited types of content, the reach of audiences, the global nature of communication". This view suggests addition rather than replacement. To be called New Media, a medium must have 4 basic elements, namely:

- a. Computing and Information Technology, to be referred to as New Media, a medium (mass media) must at least have elements

information, communication and technology there can't be just one in the body.

- b. Communication network, a media must have the ability to form a communication network between its users.
- c. Digitized Media and Content, which is considered relevant to be referred to as new media. Currently, mass media is capable of presenting digital media and content.
- d. Convergence New Media must be able to interact with other media (both traditional and modern) because the essence of convergence is the integration of one media with other media (Lievrouw & Livingstone, 2006).

METHODOLOGY

The research method used in this research is a qualitative research method. According to Suryono (2010), qualitative research is research that is used to investigate, discover, describe and explain the qualities or features of social influence that cannot be explained, measured or described through a quantitative approach. The method implemented in this research is to find out in depth about the role of TikTok social media among class XI IPA students by conducting interviews with TikTok users at Cimenteng High School to dig up in-depth information.

In this research the author uses a phenomenological approach, the etymological meaning of the word phenomenology is that it comes from phenomenon and logos. Phenomenon comes from the Greek verb, namely "phainesthai" which means to appear, and is a synonym for the words fantasy, fantom, and phosphorus which means light or light.

Phenomenology is an approach started by Edmund Husserl and developed by Martin Heidegger to understand or study human life experiences. In this research, the researcher wants to explore in depth the social phenomenon that is occurring in all circles, namely the global use of social media TikTok, especially in class

In this research, the researcher carried out an interview technique by face to face between the researcher and the resource person, the aim of conducting the interview was only the researcher and the resource person, namely so that the resource person could be more flexible in answering the researcher's questions, so that he could provide answers openly until the researcher found in-depth answers to the questions asked. by researchers regarding the role of social media TikTok in shaping the narcissistic behavior of class XI Science students at Cimenteng High School. And also use library study techniques. Literature study is a data collection method that is directed at searching for data and information through documents, both written documents, photographs, drawings and electronic documents that can support the writing process.

The subjects in this research were students of class XI Science, where this research was carried out at Cimenteng Pagelaran High School. Meanwhile, the object of this research is the role of social media TikTok in shaping students' narcissistic behavior.

RESEARCH RESULTS

There are several results from using TikTok social media in shaping students' narcissistic behavior. TikTok is an application made by a Chinese technology company, *Byte Dance Inc*, which was officially launched in September 2016. This application is used by September users to upload their own videos which can ultimately be shared with the application's users. The presence of TikTok in Indonesia began in 2017. Viv Gong, as *Head Of Marketing*, said that Indonesia is one of the main targets for his company's products. Capitalizing on the statistics of internet users which continue to increase in Indonesia, Gong believes the application can develop in Indonesia (Nolimit.id/12/07/2018).

The place where this research was conducted was in class XI of SMA Cimenteng Pagelaran. Cimenteng High School is one of the schools on New Block street, Mekarsari Village, Pagelaran District, Cianjur Regency, West Java Province.

TikTok User Data

Figure 1 TikTok User Data

From the results of a survey conducted through distribution *link google form* of class XI Science students at Cimenteng Pagelaran High School, 92% have TikTok social media accounts, the number of students at Cimenteng High School is 368 students. Almost all of the students at Cimenteng High School already have TikTok social media accounts. In this research, the author determined several informants to answer the research problem formulation. Among them:

Table 1 Informant Data

No.	Name	Social Media Accounts
1.	Silvia Dian Sara	TikTok : @Siisiilllll
2.	When Mira	TikTok: @meyyysssssss
3.	Putri Endah Nurhikmah	TikTok: @cloudkiss.x

Source: Processed by Researchers

DISCUSSION

To find out how social media is used by class XI Science students at Cimenteng High School. The following are the results of an interview with one of the class XI science students. *"According to Silvia Dian Sara, in one day you can open TikTok 6 times or more, and if you accumulate 6 hours in one day, considering that you have an online shop whose sales media uses TikTok social media, therefore besides Used as a medium to express oneself, TikTok social media is used to sell by promoting the goods it will sell through social media content."* Meanwhile, the narrative is different from that of his classmates. *"According to Putri Endah Nurhikmah, there are countless times a day when you open TikTok, because you open your gadget just to open TikTok and if you accumulate it, it can take up to 5 hours in one day."*

Meanwhile, the recommendation for high school students to use gadgets is 2 hours per day, but now it seems that has started to shift. There is a shift in the ideal time for using gadgets, considering that since the pandemic entered Indonesia, students can only use gadgets to support the teaching and learning process because it is recommended by the government to implement lockdown or advice to just stay at home.

Based on the results of an interview regarding the negative side of using TikTok social media with one of the social media activists in Cianjur, namely Mr. Fikri Andhika Hardiansyah, M.I.Kom Fundrising & Partnership Director Of(NXG),one of the communities operating in the field of literacy digital which provides insight into digital literacy. *"Well, the negative side also depends on which side we look at it from. In my opinion, currently people are still not wise in using TikTok. Not only TikTok but other social media are the same, in Indonesia there are still problems with screen time or playing duration."*

If you look at the excerpt from the interview with Mr. Fikri Andhika Hardiansyah, M.I.Kom as the triangulation of sources in this research, excessive use of social media can be a negative side because it has entered the addiction stage. As for how to actually use the gadget itself.

"According to him, actually now we can't divide the hours themselves, but for screen time, for example, for children, it can't be more than 2 hours. So, for example, if you are in middle school and high school, now during the pandemic, gadgets have become an important thing, you just have to limit yourself, how can we detox gadgets and so on, that's what we can handle. Well, actually we just have to set the duration of playing. For teenagers and children, how can we arrange between needs and entertainment, what is the division between studying and playing with this gadget?"

Reported from the Beauty Journal.CO.ID page screen time Using gadgets at the age of teenagers, parents can trust them to have several personal gadgets to meet their needs. However, the time limit for using gadgets for high school students is 2 hours per day.

Reporting from the REPUBLIKA.CO.ID page, JAKARTA teenagers are one of the age groups most affected during the Covid-19 pandemic. The reason is, the education sector has become diverted through the online system. According to international researchers, the use of screens or screen time among teenagers has doubled every day during the pandemic.

The journal authors said that research on screen use may be increasing steadily and may be caused by factors driven by structural and systemic racism. Therefore, future researchers should examine trends in screen use after pandemic restrictions are lifted and explore methods to prevent sociodemographic disparities.

In this research, the theory used for new media is the type of media that uses digital technology, for example social media and internet use. This is the opposite of old media, which refers to traditional forms of media, such as print media, for example newspapers and magazines, television and radio. Although they are all examples of mass media, potential new media audience much bigger than traditional media such as newspapers.

Theory new media which is a theory of media development when linked to research, that technological advances, especially media, play a big role in today's life. The reason is that in this era everything can be obtained by just accessing the internet, starting with information, references you want to look for and many others. The use of media will have a good impact if used wisely, the emergence of social media TikTok, for example, if social media TikTok is used wisely it will have a positive impact, on the other hand, if it is not used wisely social media can have negative effects, one of which is excessive narcissistic behavior. so that could cause over sharing, and there is no filter which can be public consumption and which cannot.

Forms of Narcissistic Behavior in Class XI Students of Cimenteng Pagelaran High School

The concept of narcissism was introduced by Sigmund Freud, one of Freud's most popular theories of narcissism explains narcissism as a feeling of love for oneself accompanied by a tendency to be self-centered, amazed at oneself so that one pays great attention to one's abilities or beauty. Based on the results of an interview with one of the informants when asked about one form of narcissistic behavior on TikTok social media. *"It turns out that there has been a change in behavior between after and before using TikTok social media, one of which is increased self-confidence because I see other people's content showing their beauty. I also subconsciously follow this trend, plus there is a filter feature that can beautify it."* Not only that, when interviewing the homeroom teacher about the forms of narcissistic behavior in class XI Science students when using the social media TikTok. *"It is true that nowadays there is great concern about the use of gadgets, especially social media, but usually there is content that is inappropriate for a student to create such content, such as dancing, but on the other hand, the school always gives direction to the students, especially you as the homeroom teacher in class XI. IPA."*

Below are several TikTok social media accounts of informants in class XI Science at SMA Cimenteng Pagelaran.

Figure 2 Informant's TikTok social media account

This is one of the informant's TikTok social media accounts. It can be seen that on average the content created and uploaded is only about showing beauty wrapped in filters available on TikTok social media which is added with music to add a cool impression to the content.

Figure 3 Informant 2's social media account

This is the second informant's TikTok social media account with 465 followers. It can be seen that the content created and uploaded is similar to the first informant. Where there is only content that shows the special side of his face which is supported by the use of filters on TikTok social media.

Figure 4 Social media accounts of informant 3

Lastly, this is the third informant's TikTok social media account, with the same type of content. It can be seen that one form of narcissistic behavior in class.

Quoted from the Merriam Webster Dictionary, narcissism is behavior that shows or is characterized by excessive attention to oneself, especially to one's physical appearance. However, the form of narcissistic behavior in the informants in this study can be considered normal, because they still pay attention to what is appropriate for public consumption and what is not for public consumption. Some informants also use TikTok social media as a place to search for self-identity, because of the breadth of content available on social media, TikTok users can widely share their feelings and tell their stories through TikTok social media, and sometimes there are some users who go viral because they have told their expressions. his heart on social media TikTok. As written in the book *Mass Communication Theory* (McQuail, 2011) that new media is also a public communication institution private, and regulated (or not) appropriately.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of research at Cimenteng Pagelaran High School, it can be concluded that TikTok social media has a role in shaping students' narcissistic behavior. From the description of the previous chapter, researchers can conclude that social media is attractive to its users, where users feel free and feel free to upload the content they create, because they see and follow existing trends. By using social media, the informant felt that his self-confidence increased until finally narcissistic behavior was formed.

The use of TikTok social media among students at Cimenteng Pagelaran High School is quite diverse and they have been familiar with TikTok social media since 2021 on average. The intensity of use is quite high, an average of 2 hours per day, but the highest time for using TikTok social media is 6 hours per day. What is the cause of the high intensity of use of TikTok social media among informants is that TikTok social media has its own interests, because the content on TikTok social media is very diverse which makes users feel entertained by the content in this media.

TikTok social media has a role in shaping students' narcissistic behavior. The emergence of social media TikTok has become a new platform for many people in all circles *content creator* which is famous for starting from the social media TikTok, this makes users compete with each other to create content so they can reach a large audience and in social media terms TikTok is *FYP (For Your Page)*. Therefore, the informants want to follow the trends on TikTok social media, this creates a challenge for TikTok social media users at Cimenteng Pagelaran High School.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusions above, in this study the researcher has several suggestions that might be implemented. Among them:

1. Theoretical Suggestions

- Researchers recommend that the results of further research carry out an in-depth study of the role of TikTok social media in building student creativity.
- For readers and social media users, researchers recommend always being wise in using social media.

2. Practical Advice

- It is hoped that Cimenteng High School will be able to utilize digital technology to promote the advantages that exist at Cimenteng High School to increase the existence of Cimenteng High School as a new school.
- Cimenteng High School students are expected to be wise in using social media and pay attention to the content created in order to produce positive content that can provide positive things to fellow students and maintain the good name of Cimenteng High School.
- For Cimenteng High School to provide insight to students to educate how important digital literacy is.

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